

Research Article

Improvement of Hay and Crops Straw Using *Chemical* Additives and Testing of *Cassia Fistula* Tree Pods as Animal Feed

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ABSTRACT

The study was undertaken at range-livestock research laboratory, El-Obeid Agricultural Research Station in the year (2012), with the objective of improving the digestibility of hay and crops straw and identifying the possibility of introducing *Cassia fistula* pods in animal feed as alternative source of protein and carbohydrates. Samples were treated using 5% urea solutions, 2% Sodium hydroxide(SH) and mixture (6% urea and 2% SH) (500ml, H₂O), Samples (Cowpea and Groundnut haulms , Sorghum and millet straws, early hay, lately hay and Roselle straw) were fermented for three periods (15, 30 and 45 days). Proximate analysis and *In vitro* digestibility were done. The experiment was arranged as factorial in an RCBD. The results showed that groundnut haulms ,sorghum straw and millet straw had the highest crude fiber content (53%, 47.5%and 42%, respectively) while cowpea and groundnut haulms recorded the highest crude protein content (16.5 and 14.5% respectively). Urea and sodium hydroxide treatments resulted in significantly increased IVDMD of cowpea hay, and groundnut haulms compared with Roselle and untreated residues, with combined urea +sodium hydroxide treatments recorded the highest IVDMDs. Fermentation for a period of 30 days had resulted in higher IVDMDs compare with period s of 15 and 45 days. Respective IVDMDs for cowpea hay for 0 (control), 15, 30 and 45 days were 65, 70, 88 and 87%, that for groundnut haulms were 65, 70, 85 and 80, and that for Roselle were 34, 45, 69 and 69%). *Cassia fistula* mature pods recorded 19 and 19.5% crude protein and fiber, while green pods were 17 and 17%. The IVDMD were 68, 62.6 and 61.48 % for green pods, leaves and mature pods respectively. The study concluded that urea, sodium hydroxide mixture and sodium hydroxide improve hay and crops residues; nutritive value in the terms of IVDMD and CP. *Cassia fistula* pods had also higher CP and IVDMD. Therefore we highly recommend the use of urea and sodium hydroxide mixture to improve hay and crops residues by fermentation for 30 days.

INTRODUCTION

The smallholder farmers in developing countries have limited resources available for feeding to their ruminant livestock. They are unable to select the basal diet according to the requirement for production unlike their more fortunate counterparts in developed countries, but use whatever is available at no or low cost. Therefore, the strategy for improving production should be to optimize the efficiency of utilization of the available feed resources, and thereby attempt to maximize animal production (Jayasurya, 2001).

Inadequate nutrition is one of the major constraints limiting livestock production in African countries. The ruminants in the smallholder sector depend on natural pasture and fibrous crop residues for their survival, growth, reproduction and production. Since quality and quantity of the natural pasture vary with season, animals dependent on it are subjected to nutritional stress in the dry season when feed resources are senesced and in short supply leading to decreased animal productivity. (DFAS, 2000)

Farmers accept that fibrous straws and stovers from cereal grain crops are a poor feed resource because their crude protein (CP) content is low and fibre levels are high. Residues are often the only livestock feed available in areas characterized by a defined dry season. The situation becomes more acute as the dry season becomes established, when protein content of the natural grazing falls, often from 12-14% to about 6-8%. The fall in crude protein content is also accompanied by an increase in fibre content. Thus, the animal is faced with insufficient amounts of a low quality and relatively indigestible feed (Saadullah et al., 2005).

In North Kordofan a large quantity of crop residues is available for livestock feeding. Crop residues are characterized by their high fiber content (>700 g of cell wall material/kg DM), low metabolized energy (<7.5 MJ/kg dry matter), low levels of crude protein (20-60 g of crude protein/kg DM) and mineral nutrients and low to moderate digestibility (<30-45% organic matter digestibility). Their daily intakes are often limited to less than 20 g dry matter/kg live weight. Most residues are also deficient in fermentable carbohydrates, reflected by the relatively low organic

- Hay harvested in February (dry)
- Hay harvested in early September (green)
- Groundnut straw
- Millet and Sorghum straws
- Roselle straw
- Cowpea hay

All samples were treated with 6% Urea + 2% sodium hydroxide (treatment 1 include the 7 sample) urea 5 % (tr2), and Sodium hydroxide (tr3) in three fermentation periods (15, 30 and 45day). Then treated samples were kept in nylon bags kept in pits covered 30 cm below soil. The total number of samples treated was 63 arranged as factorial in an RCBD. After fermentation, the 63 samples with three replications (189 samples) were prepared for in vitro digestibility. *Cassia fistula pods*

matter digestibility. Chemical treatment increases the potential feeding value of crop residues. (Homp, 1994).

Therefore, improvement in feeding value would substantially reduce the effects of underfeeding on both survivability and production. The nutritive value of residues can be improved by correct harvesting and storage, supplementation and physical and chemical treatment.

In vitro methods for laboratory estimations of degraded feeds are important for ruminant nutritionists. *In vitro* methods have the advantage not only of being less expensive than animal trials and less time-consuming, but they allow one to maintain experimental conditions more precisely than do *in vivo* trials (live animal). (Makkar, 2000). The *Cassia fistula* tree is a medium-sized tree, growing to 10–20 metres (33–66 ft) tall with fast growth. The leaves are deciduous,. The flowers are produced in pendulous racemes 20–40 centimetres The fruit is a legume, 30–60 centimetres (12–24 in) long and 1.5–2.5 centimetres (0.59–0.98 in) broad, with a pungent odour and containing several seeds. *Cassia fistula* is widely grown in tropical and subtropical areas (ILDIS, 2005). *Cassia fistula* is found naturally in west and south Kordofan region (Elnazeir, 2013).

Attempting to improve hay and crops residues and testing *Cassia fistula* as feed, would enable removing feed quality constraints and improving productivity.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In vitro digestibility trial and proximate chemical analysis for hay, crops residues and *Cassia fistula* pods (green and mature) were undertaken at range-livestock research laboratory, El-Obeid Agricultural Research Station.

Proximate Chemical analysis was done according to A.O.A.C 1980. To determine: Crude fiber (CF), Crude Protein (CP), Dry matter (DM), Ether Extract (E.E), Nitrogen free extracts (NFE) and Ash.

Samples were prepared during rainy mid of September for early hay and post harvest for other crops residues in rainy season 2012.

(green and mature) and leaves also prepared for *In vitro* Digestibility.

In vitro Digestibility

The method used in this study was done according to Tilley and Terry (1963). 250 mg from each sample were taken to a 50ml centrifuge tube. Ten ml of buffer-nutrient solution were added to them. The contents were then gently mixed. The tubes were allowed to stand at 39°C

for a short period to permit saturation of the substrate. The rumen fluid was filtered through two layers of cheese cloth to remove detached fragments then kept in thermos ready for incubation. The PH of the buffer-nutrient solution was carefully maintained at 6.8-7.0. Five ml of rumen fluid inoculums were added to each tube, and then the tube surface was flushed with CO₂ for approximately 10 seconds before stopped with gas release valve, and then incubated at 39 °C for 48 hours. The tubes were gently rotated approximately 2, 4, 20, and 28 hours after initiation of incubation to disperse the forage particles.

After 48 hours incubation, 1ml HgCl₂ solution, 2ml of Sodium carbonate solution were added, and

In vitro dry matter digestibility (IVDM) =

$$\frac{100 \times \text{Sample DM} - (\text{Resid. DM Sample} - \text{Mean. resid DM inco. blank})}{\text{Sample DM}} \times 100$$

In vitro Organic matter digestibility ((IVOMD)) =

$$\frac{100 \times \text{Sample OM} - (\text{Resid. OM Sample} - \text{Mean. resid OM inco. blank})}{\text{Sample OM}} \times 100$$

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Proximate chemical analysis and *in vitro* digestibility for hay and crop residues:

Proximate chemical composition and minerals content for hay and crops residues are presented in Table (1).

Crops residue analyzed included cowpea, sorghum straw, groundnut haulms, millet straw, roselle, early hay and lately hay. Groundnut haulms, sorghum straw and millet straw had the highest crude fiber content (53%, 47.5% and 42%, respectively) Crude protein of these crops residues varies from low to high. Cowpea and groundnut haulms recorded the highest crude protein content (16.5 and 14.5% respectively). While lately hay, sorghum straw, millet straw and roselle had the lowest crude protein content (7.5, 6.3, 4.5 and 4%, respectively). Millet straw had the highest ash value 12% while lately hay had the lowest value (9.1%). Jayasurya, (2000) stated that protein content less than 10% is considered as low protein content. A critical value of about 6.6% crude protein in feed is required (NRC, 1981), below which the apparent crude protein digestibility declines.

In vitro Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD) for hay and crops straw fermented with sodium hydroxide plus urea with different fermentation periods are illustrated in Table (2). The highest (IVDMD) was recorded after 30 and 45 days of fermentation in all samples followed by 15 days of fermentation and control (non fermented). Cowpea recorded the highest (IVDMD) (65, 70, 88 and 87%) for control, 15, 30 and 45 days of fermentation respectively; while roselle recorded the lowest values in

then centrifuged for 15 min at 2000x gravity to sediment the suspended dry matter. Then 25 ml of acid-pepsin solution were added and mixed gently rotated to re-suspend the residue at approximately, 2, 4, 20 and 48 hours after the beginning of incubation.

After 48 hours, the tube contents were filtered through tarred fritted glass crucibles, and then dried to a constant weight at 102 °C. The residue retained on the filter is indigestible dry matter; crucibles were weighted after cooling in desiccators. Then *In vitro* dry matter and organic matter digestibility were calculated using the following formula, (Tilley and Terry, 1963).

(IVDMD) (34, 45, 69 and 69%) respectively for control and the three above mentioned periods.

The results indicated that there were significant differences in (IVDMD) between periods ($P \leq 0.05$). High values achieved by cowpea; this is mainly attributed to the effect of high protein content. Chimwano, (2000) who stated that, high protein content positively affect (IVDMD). Low values achieved by Roselle; this is mainly due to high fiber content (47%) and the effect of low protein content (4%). NRC, (1981) stated that a critical value of about 6.6% crude protein in feed is required, below which the apparent crude protein digestibility declines. No significant differences were found between 30 and 45 day of fermentation. This in agreement with Smith 2000 who stated the best period for incubation for tropic is from 14 to 42 days.

In Vitro Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD) for hay and crops straw fermented with urea with different fermentation periods are shown in Table (3). The highest (IVDMD) was recorded after 30 and 45 days of fermentation in all samples followed by 15 days of fermentation and control (non-fermented). Groundnut and cowpea recorded the highest (IVDMD) (60, 65, 83 and 79%) and (60, 69, 80 and 81%) for control, 15, 30 and 45 days of fermentation respectively; while roselle recorded the lowest values in (IVDMD) (39, 55, 63 and 65%) respectively for control, 15, 30 and 45 days of fermentation. The results indicated that there were significant differences in (IVDMD) between the second and third periods compared to control ($P \leq 0.05$), but no significant differences between second and third periods. The highest values achieved by groundnut and cowpea; this is mainly due to the high protein content and to the effect of urea treatment. Saadullah *et al.*

(2005) noted that dry matter digestibility could be increased by six units when urea was added as a supplement at the point of feeding but by 11% units when it was added to the straw 10 days previously. Low values recorded by Roselle were mainly due to high fiber content and the effect of low protein content. Roy, 1979, stated that high crude fiber content and poor source of energy limits the digestibility.

In vitro Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD) for hay and crops straw fermented with sodium hydroxide with different fermentation periods are illustrated in Table (4). The highest (IVDMD) was recorded after second and third periods of fermentation in all feed stuff under study followed by first period and control (non-fermented). Ground nut and cowpea recorded the highest (IVDMD) (61, 65, 71 and 69%) and (63, 65, 70 and 69%) for control, first, second and third periods, respectively; While roselle recorded the lowest values in (IVDMD) (40, 50, 59 and 59.33%) for control, first, second and third periods. There were significant differences in (IVDMD) between periods first, second and third compared to control ($P \leq 0.05$); but no significant differences between second and third period. High values recorded by ground-nut and cowpea; this is mainly attributed to protein content and the effect of sodium hydroxide. This agreed with Homb (1994) who stated that sodium hydroxide treatment increases the potential feeding value of crop residues. Low values recorded by roselle; this is mainly due to high fiber content and the effect of low protein content. Jackson, (1980) stated that the situation becomes more acute as the dry season becomes established, when protein content of the natural grazing falls, often from 12-14% to about 6-8%. The fall in crude protein content is also accompanied by an increase in fiber content.

Thus, the animal is faced with insufficient amounts of a low quality and relatively indigestible feed. Elnazeir(2007), stated that sheep grazed under range condition the daily weight (IVDMD 52%) 0.5 g to -0.52 (optimum to critical period).

Proximate analysis and *in vitro* digestibility for *Cassia fistula* green, mature pods and leaves:

The proximate analysis for *Cassia fistula* is shown in table (5) Mature pods recorded 19, 19.5, 2.6 , 5 and

52% for CP, CF, ash, E.E and NFE respectively; while green pods recorded 17, 17, 5.5, 6 and 54.5% for the same components respectively. Jayasurya, (2000) stated that protein content greater than 10% and crude fiber less than 30%; this give the feed the class of high protein less fiber. The high values for crude protein and NFE (carbohydrates), are of value when planning for ration formulation, because those can be added as alternative cheap source of protein and carbohydrates, also this source is not competing the human foods. Mineral content for *Cassia fistula* mature pods is shown in table (5). Proximate analysis indicated that Calcium, Phosphorus and Potassium, for *cassia fistula* mature pods were 2.7, 0.8 and 0.75ppm, respectively. This reflect that the pods are rich in mineral which could be used in animal feed.

In vitro digestibility dry matter (DM) and organic matter (OM) for the mature, green pods and leaves for *Cassia fistula* are illustrated in table (6). The *in vitro* dry matter digestibility for green pods (68%) was higher than leaves (62.6%) and mature pods (61.48%). *In vitro* OM digestibility for mature pods (79.75) was the highest followed by *the leaves* (79.11%) and *green pods* (77.47%). The values for both *in vitro* digestibility dry matter (DM) and organic matter (OM) could be considered as high values compared to that of range plants, approximately 51% and 57% for IVDMD and OVDMD, respectively (Elnazeir 2007). High protein and less fiber class; this indicates that cassia fistula can be used as ruminant and poultry feed. Cassia fistula pods reflect good indicator in reducing the ration cost up to 25 % when tested in Feedsoft@2010 program for ration formulation.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the presented data it can be concluded that urea, sodium hydroxide mixture and sodium hydroxide improve hay and crops residues digestibility (10-35%). *Cassia fistula* is a promising tree due to high nutritive value particularly in protein content and high IVDMD.

Therefore; we highly recommend the use of 2 %sodium hydroxide ,6%urea and urea sodium hydroxide mixture to improve hay and crops residues by fermentation for (30) days.

Table. 1. Proximate analysis for hay and crops straw

Sample	DM	CP	CF	E.E	Moisture	Ash	NFE	OM
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Cowpea	93	16.5	29	1.9	6.5	10.3	44.8	83
Sorghum straw	94	6.3	47.5	1.3	5.5	9.11	31.3	85
Groundnut holms	93.5	14.5	53	2	5.6	10.5	14.9	83.1
Millet straw	94	4.5	42	1	4.9	12.6	35	81
Early hay	94.5	10.5	38	1.3	5	9.2	36	85
Lately Hay	95	7.5	31	1.1	5	9.1	46.3	85
Roselle	93.7	4	47	1.	4.8	10	33.2	84
S.E	0.216	1.7	3.39	0.184	0.202	0.53	3.9	.02
Mean	94	8.8	41	1.29	5.43	10	34.4	

Table (2) The *In Vitro* Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD) for hay and crops straw fermented with sodium hydroxide plus urea.

Sample	DM	IVDMD control	IVDMD 15day	IVDMD 30day	IVDMD 45 day
Cowpea	93	65	70	88	87
Sorghum straw	94	44	54	76	78
Groundnut holms	93.5	65	70	85	84
Millet straw	94	44	65	76	73
Early hay	94.5	63	70	83	81
Lately Hay	95	43	55	70	72
Roselle	93.7	34	45	69	69
S.E	0.218	4.58	3.77	2.5	2.7
Mean	94	51	61.2	77.7	78.14

DM=Dry Matter, IVDMD=In Vitro Dry Matter Digestibility,

Table (3) The *In Vitro* Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD) for hay and crops straw fermented with urea.

Sample	DM	IVDMD control	IVDMD 15day	IVDMD 30day	IVDMD 45 day
Cowpea	93	60	65	83	79
Sorghum straw	94	40	52	70	72
Groundnut holms	93.5	60	69	80	81
Millet straw	94	44	60	72	74
Early hay	94.5	60	68	78	76
Lately Hay	95	40	50	75	72
Roselle	93.7	39	55	63	65
Mean	94	49	59	74	7
S.E	0.218	3.39	2.92	2.55	1.9

DM=Dry Matter, IVDMD=In Vitro Dry Matter Digestibility,

Table (4) The *In vitro* Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD for hay and crops straw fermented with sodium hydroxide

Sample	DM	IVDMD control	IVDMD 15day	IVDMD 30day	IVDMD 45 day
Cowpea	93	63	65	70	69
Sorghum straw	94	43	50	66	65
Groundnut holms	93.5	61	65	71	69
Millet straw	94	38	58	72	74
Early hay	94.5	64	68	78	76
Lately Hay	95	45	50	75	72
Roselle	93.7	40	50	59	59.33
Mean	94	50	58	70	69
S.E±	0.22	4.37	3.05	2.34	2.18

DM=Dry Matter, IVDMD=In Vitro Dry Matter Digestibility,

Proximate analysis for cassia fistula is in table (5)

Feed	DM	Protein	Fiber	Ash	oil	NFE	Ca ppm	P ppm	K ppm
Mature pods	93.4	19	19.5	2.6	5	52.6	2.7	0.81	0.75
Green pods	94	17	17	5.5	6	54.5	-	-	-
SE±	0.5	1	1.5	0.5	0.3	6.5	0.005	0.055	0.01

Table (6) The *In vitro* Dry Matter Digestibility (IVDMD for Mature pods, Green pods and leaves of *Cassia fistula* tree.

Source	DM	IVDMD	IVOM
Mature pods	93.4	61.48	79.75
Green pods	94	68.16	77.47
leaves	97.1	62.60	79.11
Mean	94.6	64	78.8
SE±	2.1	3.6	1.53

DM=Dry Matter, IVDMD=In Vitro Dry Matter Digestibility, IVOM= Vitro Organic Matter Digestibility

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